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Fuzzy Isomorphism Theorem

By

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ABSTRACT

In 1965, the concept of fuzzy sets was introduced by (Zadeh L.A.) and in 1982 ,(Liu W.J.) introduced the concept of fuzzy rings, fuzzy ideals and since that time many papers were introduced in different mathematical scopes of theoretical and practical applications. In 1993 ,(Liu W.J.) introduced the concept of fuzzy submodule. A characterization of rings which are both homomorphism and isomorphism is obtained. We are proving to the fuzzy rings whose fuzzy ideals assume to obtain it. Kernal fuzzy have been defined and conditions have been obtained under which we need.

SECTION ONE BASIC CONCEPTS

This section contains some definitions and properties of fuzzy subset, fuzzy ring, fuzzy ideal, fuzzy submodule which we will be used in the next chapter.

1.1 PRELIMINARY CONCEPTS

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring. A **fuzzy subset of R** is a function from R into $[0,1]$,in my paper , $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a commutative ring with identity , ([1] , [2]) .

Let A and B be fuzzy subset of R. We write $A \subseteq B$ if $A(x) \leq B(x)$ for all $x \in R$. If $A \subseteq B$ and there exists $x \in R$ such that $A(x) < B(x)$, then we write $A \subset B$ and we say that A is a proper fuzzy subset of B, [1] . Note that $A = B$ if and only if $A(x) = B(x)$, for all $x \in R$, ([1] , [3]) .

For each $t \in [0,1]$, the set $A_t = \{ x \in R \mid A(x) \geq t \}$ is called a **level subset of R** and the set $A_* = \{ x \in R \mid A(x) = A(0) \}$, ([1] , [4]) .

Let A and B be fuzzy subsets of R, **the product $A \circ B$** define by :

$A \circ B (x) = \sup \{ A(y), B(z) \mid x = y \cdot z \}$, $y, z \in R$, for all $x \in R$, [2] .

Let A and B be fuzzy subsets of R, **the addition $A+B$** define by :

$A+B(x) = \sup \{A(y), B(z)\} | x = y+z \}$ $y, z \in R$, for all $x \in R$, [2].

We let ϕ denote $\phi(x) = 0$ for all $x \in R$, **the empty fuzzy subset of R**, ([3], [5]).

Let A be a non empty fuzzy subset of R , A is called **a fuzzy subgroup of R** if for all $x, y \in R$, $A(x+y) \geq \min \{A(x), A(y)\}$ and $A(x) = A(-x)$, [5].

A is a non empty fuzzy subset of R , A is called **a fuzzy ring of R** if and only if for all $x, y \in R$, then $A(x-y) \geq \min \{A(x), A(y)\}$ and $A(x \cdot y) \geq \min \{A(x), A(y)\}$, ([3], [5]).

A non empty fuzzy subset A of R is called **a fuzzy ideal of R** if and only if for all $x, y \in R$, then $A(x-y) \geq \min \{A(x), A(y)\}$ and $A(x \cdot y) \geq \max \{A(x), A(y)\}$, ([1], [5]). It is clear that every fuzzy ideal of R is a fuzzy ring of R , but the converse is not true.

Let X be a fuzzy ring of R and A be a fuzzy ideal of R such that $A \subseteq X$. Then A is **a fuzzy ideal of the fuzzy ring X**, [6].

If A is a fuzzy ideal of R , then A^* and A_t are ideals of R , ([1], [4]).

In my paper, $L \approx [0,1]$ when L is **a complete distributive lattice**, ([1], [2]).

Let X be a non empty fuzzy ring of a ring R , M be a module. The fuzzy subset B of M is called **a fuzzy submodules over a fuzzy ring X** if for all $x, y \in M$ and $r \in R$, we have: 1) $B(x-y) \geq \min \{B(x), B(y)\}$.

2) $B(r \cdot x) \geq \min \{X(r), B(x)\}$.

3) $B(0) = 1$, [7]. Now we can take $B(0) = X(0)$ in L .

If A is a fuzzy submodule over a fuzzy ring X of R , then A^* is module of R , ([7], [8]). If A is a fuzzy submodule of a fuzzy ring X of R , then A_t is module of a ring X_t , [7].

1.2 HOMOMORPHISM FUNCTIONS

In this section, we shall give some concepts about homomorphism and isomorphism functions. Also, we give some properties of these concepts.

DEFINITION 1.2.1 [9]:

A mapping f from a ring $(R, +, \cdot)$ to a ring $(R', +', \cdot')$ is called ring homomorphism if it satisfies the following properties for all $a, b \in R$:

1. $f(a + b) = f(a) +' f(b)$
2. $f(a \cdot b) = f(a) \cdot' f(b)$.

PROPOSITION 1.2.2:

If $f : R \rightarrow R'$ and $g : R' \rightarrow R''$ are homomorphism between the fuzzy subsets A , B and C , then $f \circ g$ is a homomorphism between A and C .

PROOF:

$A : R \rightarrow [0,1]$, $B : R' \rightarrow [0,1]$ and $C : R'' \rightarrow [0,1]$ are fuzzy subsets, f and g are homomorphism such that :

To prove that $f \circ g$ is a homomorphism, let $a, b \in R$, then

1. $g \circ f(a + b) = g(f(a + b)) = g(f(a) + f(b)) = g(f(a)) + g(f(b))$
 $= g \circ f(a) + g \circ f(b)$
2. $g \circ f(a \cdot b) = g(f(a \cdot b)) = g(f(a) \cdot f(b)) = g(f(a)) \cdot g(f(b))$
 $= g \circ f(a) \cdot g \circ f(b)$

Hence $g \circ f$ is a homomorphism between A and C .

REMARK 1.2.3 :

1. If f and g are isomorphism, then $g \circ f$ is an isomorphism since f and g are 1 – 1 and onto implies that $g \circ f$ is 1 – 1 and onto.
2. If f and g are homomorphism , 1 – 1 and onto, then $g \circ f$ is an isomorphism .

PROPOSITION 1.2.4 :

Let A be fuzzy submodule of M over a fuzzy ring X , B be a fuzzy submodule of M' over a fuzzy ring Y . $f : M \rightarrow M'$ be an epimorphism , then :

1. $f(A)$ is a fuzzy submodule of M' .
2. $f^{-1}(B)$ is a fuzzy submodule of M .

PROOF:

(1) Let $x, y \in M'$ such that $f(a) = x, f(b) = y$, where $a, b \in M$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{a) } f(A)(x - y) &= \sup \{ \min \{ A(a), A(b) \} \mid a = f^{-1}(x), b = f^{-1}(y) \} . \\
 &\geq \sup \{ \min \{ X(a), A(b) \} \mid a = f^{-1}(x), b = f^{-1}(y) \} . \\
 &= \sup \{ \min \{ Y(x), f(A)(y) \} \mid x = f(a), y = f(b) \} . \\
 &\geq \sup \{ \min \{ f(A)(x), f(A)(y) \} \mid x = f(a), y = f(b) \} , [10] . \\
 &\geq \min \{ f(A)(x), f(A)(y) \} .
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{b) } f(A)(r \cdot x) &= \sup \{ \min \{ A(r'), A(a) \} \mid r' = f^{-1}(r), a = f^{-1}(x), f(r) = r', r \in R \text{ and } r' \in R' . \\
 &\geq \sup \{ \min \{ X(r'), A(a) \} \mid r' = f^{-1}(r), a = f^{-1}(x) \} .
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= \sup \{ \min \{ Y(r), f(A)(x) \} \mid r = f(r'), x = f(a) \} .$$

$$\geq \min \{ Y(r), f(A)(x) \} .$$

c) Because A is a fuzzy submodule of M over a fuzzy ring X , for any $x \in M$, we have $A(0) = 1 \geq A(x)$,so $f(A)(0') = \max \{ A(x) \mid x \in f^{-1}(0') \} = A(0) = 1$.

Hence $f(A)$ is a fuzzy submodule of M' .

(2) Let $a, b \in M$ such that $f^{-1}(x) = a, f^{-1}(y) = b$, where $x, y \in M'$

$$\text{a) } f^{-1}(B)(a - b) = \sup \{ \min \{ B(x), B(y) \} \mid x = f(a), y = f(b) \} .$$

$$\geq \sup \{ \min \{ Y(x), B(y) \} \mid x = f(a), y = f(b) \} .$$

$$= \sup \{ \min \{ X(a), f^{-1}(B)(b) \} \mid a = f^{-1}(x), b = f^{-1}(y) \} .$$

$$\geq \sup \{ \min \{ f^{-1}(B)(a), f^{-1}(B)(b) \} \mid a = f^{-1}(x), b = f^{-1}(y) \} \text{ by [10] .}$$

$$\geq \min \{ f^{-1}(B)(a), f^{-1}(B)(b) \} .$$

$$\text{b) } f^{-1}(B)(r \cdot b) = \sup \{ \min \{ B(r'), B(y) \} \mid r' = f(r), y = f(b) \}, f(r) = r', r \in R \text{ and } r' \in R' .$$

$$\geq \sup \{ \min \{ Y(r'), B(y) \} \mid r' = f(r), y = f(b) \} .$$

$$= \sup \{ \min \{ X(r), f^{-1}(B)(b) \} \mid r = f^{-1}(r'), b = f^{-1}(y) \} .$$

$$\geq \min \{ X(r), f^{-1}(B)(b) \} .$$

c) Because B is a fuzzy submodule of M' over a fuzzy ring Y , , for any $y \in M'$, we have $B(0') = 1 \geq B(y)$,so $f^{-1}(B)(0') = \max \{ B(y) \mid y \in f(0) \} = B(0') = 1$.

Hence $f^{-1}(B)$ is a fuzzy submodule of M' .

1.3 QUOTIENT FUZZY RING

In this section, we shall give definition and some properties of quotient fuzzy ring.

DEFINITION 1.3.1 [8]:

Let X is a fuzzy ring of R and A is a fuzzy ideal in X.

Define $X/A : R/A_* \rightarrow [0,1]$ such that:

$$X/A(a + A_*) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a \in A_* \\ \sup \{ X(a + b) \} & \text{if } a \notin A_*, b \in A_* \end{cases}$$

For all $a + A_* \in R/A_*$, X/A is called a **quotient fuzzy ring of X by A**.

Note that : X/A is a fuzzy ring of R/A_* by remark (3. 3 .1. 2) in [8] .

PROPOSITION 1.3.2 [8]:

1. X is a fuzzy ring of R and A is a fuzzy ideal in X , then

$$X/A(0 + A^*) = 1, \quad [0 + A^* = A^*].$$

2. If X is a fuzzy ring of R and A and B are fuzzy ideals in X such that $A \subseteq B$. Then

$B/A : R/A^* \rightarrow [0,1]$ such that

$$B/A(a + A^*) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a \in A^* \\ \sup\{B(a + b)\} & \text{if } a \notin A^*, b \in A^* \end{cases}$$

is a fuzzy ideal in X/A .

3. Let X be a fuzzy ring of R such that $X(0) = 1$ and A be a fuzzy ideal in X . Define

$K : R/A^* \rightarrow [0,1]$ such that $K(a + A^*) = \sup \{ X(a + b) \mid b \in A^* \}$. Then $X/A = K$.

PROPOSITION 1.3.3:

Let I be a module and R be a ring, A be a fuzzy submodule over a fuzzy ring X of R . Then the fuzzy subset B of R/I define by $B(a + I) = \sup \{ A(a + x) \mid x \in I \}$ is a fuzzy submodule of the quotient ring in R/I .

PROOF:

Define $B : R/I \rightarrow [0,1]$ such that $B(a + I) = \sup \{ A(a + x) \mid x \in I \}$

since $B(0 + I) = A(0)$, B is non empty fuzzy subset of R/I .

Let $a + I, b + I \in R/I$, $a + I = b + I$, then $b = a + c$, for some $c \in I$.

$$B(a + I) = \sup \{ A(b + x) \mid x \in I \} = \sup \{ A(a + c + x) \mid x \in I \}.$$

$$= \sup \{ A(a + y) \mid y = x + c \in I \} = B(b + I).$$

Hence B is a well – defined.

Now, we must prove B is a fuzzy submodule of R/I .

1. $B[(a + I) - (b + I)] = B[(a - b) + I] = \sup \{ A((a - b) + x) \mid x \in I \}.$
 $= \sup \{ A((a - b) + (v - w)) \mid x = v - w \in I \}.$
 $= \sup \{ A((a + v) - (b + w)) \mid w, v \in I \}.$
 $\geq \sup \{ \min \{ A(a + v), A(b + w) \} \},$ since A is fuzzy submodule .
 $\geq \min \{ \sup \{ A(a + v) \mid v \in I \}, \sup \{ A(b + w) \mid w \in I \} \}.$
 $= \min \{ B(a + I), B(b + I) \}.$

Then $B[(a + I) - (b + I)] \geq \min \{ B(a + I), B(b + I) \}.$

2. $B[(r + I) \cdot (b + I)] = B[(r \cdot b) + I] = \sup \{ A((r \cdot b) + x) \mid x \in I \}, (r + I) \in R/I.$
 $\geq \sup \{ \min \{ X(a + v), A(b + w) \} \mid v, w \in I \},$ since A is fuzzy submodule .
 $\geq \min \{ \sup \{ X(a + v) \mid v \in I \}, \sup \{ A(b + w) \mid w \in I \} \}.$

$$= \min \{ A(a + I), B(b + I) \}.$$

Implies that $B[(r + I) \cdot (b + I)] \geq \min \{ A(r + I), B(b + I) \}.$

$$3. \quad B(0 + I) = \sup \{ A(a + x) \mid x \in I \}, 0 \in R.$$

$$= A(0) = 1.$$

Then $B(0 + I) = A(0) = 1.$

Hence B is a fuzzy submodule of $R / I.$

PROPOSITION 1.3.4 :

Let $X : R \rightarrow L$ be a fuzzy ring and A be a fuzzy submodule in $X.$ Then

$f : R \rightarrow R / A^*$ define by: $f(a) = a + A^*$ is homomorphism between X and $X / A.$

PROOF:

$f : R \rightarrow R / A^*$ such that $f(a) = a + A^*.$ Let $a, b \in R$

$$f(a + b) = (a + b) + A^* = (a + A^*) \oplus (b + A^*) = f(a) \oplus f(b)$$

$$f(a \cdot b) = (a \cdot b) + A^* = (a + A^*) \otimes (b + A^*) = f(a) \otimes f(b)$$

Hence f is a homomorphism between X and $X / A.$

Note that : since for any $a + A^* \in R / A^*, a + A^* = f(a),$ then f is onto.

PROPOSITION 1.3.5 :

Let X be a fuzzy ring of R and A be a fuzzy submodule of $X.$ Let I be a module of R maximal among those contained in $A^* \cap X^*.$ Then there exists a bijection between the fuzzy submodules of X / A and the fuzzy submodules A of X such that $I \subseteq A^*.$

PROOF:

Let $B = \{A' \mid A' \text{ fuzzy submodule of } X, I \subseteq A^*\}, C = \{A'' \mid A'' \text{ fuzzy submodule of } X / A\}.$ $f : R \rightarrow R / I$ such that $f(a) = a + I, a \in R.$ Note that f is a homomorphism by proposition (1.3.3).

Let $h : B \rightarrow C$ such that : $h(A') = f(A'), h(A')(a) = a + I.$

$k : C \rightarrow B$ such that : $k(A'') = f^{-1}(A''), k(A'')(a + I) = a.$

Now, to prove that $k \circ h = i_B, h \circ k = i_C.$

$$(k \circ h)(A')(x) = k(h(A')(x)), x \in R = f^{-1}(f(A')(x)).$$

$$= \sup \{A'(y) \mid y \in f^{-1}(f(x))\} = \sup \{A'(x + z) \mid z \in I\} = A'(x).$$

Therefore $k \circ h = i_B.$

$$(h \circ k)(A'')(y) = h(k(A'')(y)), y \in R / I.$$

$$= f(f^{-1}(A'')(y)) = \sup \{A''(x + z) \mid z \in I, x \in f^{-1}(y)\}.$$

$$= \sup\{A''(y) \mid y \in f(f^{-1}(x))\} = A''(y) .$$

Hence $h \circ k = ic$.

Now, we must prove that k, h are bijection .

$1 - 1$: $h(x) = h(y)$, then $x + I = y + I$ implies that $x - y \in I$ and $x = y$, h is $1 - 1$.

$k(x + I) = k(y + I)$, then $x = y$, k is $1 - 1$.

onto : for all $x \in R$, there exists $y \in R$ such that $x = y + z$, $z \in I$, then $x \in y + I$,

hence k is onto.

For all $x \in R$, there exists $y \in R$ such that $y \in x + I$ implies that $z \in I$, $y = x + z$,

hence h is onto .

Then there exists a bijection between the fuzzy submodules of X/A and the fuzzy submodules A of X such that $I \subseteq A^*$.

SECTION TWO

2.1 FUZZY KERNEL AND FUZZY NORMAL

Now, we shall introduce the concept of a fuzzy kernel of a function and some properties of it and we shall introduce the concept of a normal fuzzy of a function and some properties of it.

DEFINITION 2.1.1 ([9], [10]):

Let $X : R \rightarrow [0,1]$, $Y : R' \rightarrow [0,1]$ are fuzzy sets . $f : R \rightarrow R'$ be homomorphism between them. We define **the fuzzy kernel of f** , $\ker f_{zz}f : R \rightarrow [0,1]$ by :

$$\ker f_{zz}f(x) = \begin{cases} X(0) & x \in \ker f \\ 0 & x \notin \ker f \end{cases}$$

PROPOSITION 2.1.2 [10]:

$\ker f_{zz}f : R \rightarrow [0,1]$ is a fuzzy ideal of a fuzzy ring X .

PROPOSITION 2.1.3:

$\ker f_{zz}f : R \rightarrow L$ is a fuzzy submodule of a fuzzy ring X .

PROOF:

Since $\ker f_{zz}f(0) = X(0)$, then $\ker f_{zz}f \equiv \phi$, let $x, y, r \in R$, then

1. If $x - y \in \ker f$, hence

$$\ker f_{zz}f(x - y) = X(0) \geq \min \{ \ker f_{zz}f(x), \ker f_{zz}f(y) \}.$$

2. If $x - y \notin \ker f$, then $x \notin \ker f$, $y \notin \ker f$

$$\ker f_{zz}f(x - y) = 0 = \min \{ \ker f_{zz}f(x), \ker f_{zz}f(y) \}.$$

3. If $x \notin \ker f$, then $\ker f_{zzf}(x) = 0 \leq X(x)$ and

If $x \in \ker f$, then $\ker f_{zzf}(x) = X(0) = X(x) = Y(0) = Y(x)$.

$x - y \notin \ker f$, hence $\ker f_{zzf}(x - y) = 0 = \min \{ \ker f_{zzf}(x), \ker f_{zzf}(y) \}$.

Therefore $\ker f_{zzf}(x - y) \geq \min \{ \ker f_{zzf}(x), \ker f_{zzf}(y) \}$.

1- If $r \cdot y \in \ker f$, hence $\ker f_{zzf}(r \cdot y) = X(0) \geq \min \{ X(r), \ker f_{zzf}(y) \}$.

2- If $r \cdot y \notin \ker f$, then $y \notin \ker f$, $\ker f_{zzf}(r \cdot y) = 0 = \min \{ X(r), \ker f_{zzf}(y) \}$.

Therefore $\ker f_{zzf}(r \cdot y) \geq \min \{ X(r), \ker f_{zzf}(y) \}$.

Note that ,by defection (2.1.1) , if $x \in \ker f$, $\ker f_{zzf}(x) = X(0)$ and if $x \notin \ker f$, then $\ker f_{zzf}(x) = 0$. Then $\ker f_{zzf}(x) = X(0)$.

Hence , $\ker f_{zzf}$ is a fuzzy submodule of a fuzzy ring X .

DEFINITION 2.1.4 [10] :

A fuzzy ideal A of a fuzzy ring X of R is called **normal** if $A(x^{-1} \cdot y \cdot x) \geq \min \{X(x), A(y)\}$ for all $x, y \in R$.

PROPOSITION 2.1.5 [10] :

Let A be a fuzzy ideal of a fuzzy ring X of R . If A is a normal fuzzy ideal, $A(0) \geq t$, then A_t is a normal ideal of X_t .

PROPOSITION 2.1.6 [10] :

$\ker f_{zzf} : R \rightarrow [0,1]$ is a normal fuzzy ideal of X .

PROPOSITION 2.1.7 [11] :

Let A be a fuzzy submodule of a fuzzy ring X of R . If A is a normal fuzzy submodule, then A_t is a normal submodule of X_t , for all $t \in [0, A(0)]$.

PROPOSITION 2.1.8 :

$\ker f_{zzf} : R \rightarrow L$ is a normal fuzzy submodule of X .

PROOF:

By proposition (2.1.3) $\ker f_{zzf}$ is fuzzy submodule of X . We must prove that $\ker f_{zzf}$ is normal (i.e. let $a, b \in R$, $\ker f_{zzf}(a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a) \geq \min \{ \ker f_{zzf}(b), X(a) \}$).

1. If $a \in \ker f$, then $a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a \in \ker f$ and

$$\ker f_{zzf}(a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a) = X(0) \geq \min \{ \ker f_{zzf}(b), X(a) \}$$

2. If $a \notin \ker f$, then either $a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a \in \ker f$ or $a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a \notin \ker f$

$$a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a \in \ker f \text{ implies that } \ker f_{zzf}(a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a) = X(0) \geq \min \{ \ker f_{zzf}(b), X(a) \}$$

$$a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a \notin \ker f \text{ implies that } \ker f_{zzf}(a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a) = 0 = \min \{ \ker f_{zzf}(b), X(a) \}$$

Hence $\ker f_{zz}f$ is a normal fuzzy submodule of X .

PROPOSITION 2.1.9 [10] :

Let $X : R \rightarrow [0,1]$, $Y : R' \rightarrow [0,1]$ are fuzzy rings $f : R \rightarrow R'$ be homomorphism between them and $A : R \rightarrow [0,1]$ is a fuzzy ideal of X and $B : R' \rightarrow [0,1]$ is a fuzzy ideal of Y , then

1. $f(A)$ is normal fuzzy ideal of Y , if A is normal and f is subjective.
2. $f^{-1}(B)$ is normal fuzzy ideal of X , if B is normal.

PROPOSITION 2.1.10 :

Let $X : R \rightarrow [0,1]$, $Y : R' \rightarrow [0,1]$ are fuzzy rings $f : R \rightarrow R'$ be homomorphism between them and A is a fuzzy submodule of X and B is a fuzzy submodule of Y , then :

1. $f(A)$ is normal fuzzy submodule of Y , if A is normal and f is subjective.
2. $f^{-1}(B)$ is normal fuzzy submodule of X , if B is normal.

PROOF:

(1) $f(A)$ is fuzzy submodule of Y by proposition (1.2.4). Now, we must prove that $f(A)$ is normal.

Let $x, y \in R'$ such that $f(a) = x, f(b) = y$, where $a, b \in R$.

$$\begin{aligned} f(A) (x^{-1} \cdot y \cdot x) &= f(A)(f(a^{-1}) \cdot f(b) \cdot f(a)) = f[A(a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a)] \geq f[\min \{ A(b), X(a) \}] \\ &= \sup \{ \min \{ \min \{ A(b), X(a) \} \mid a = f^{-1}(x), b = f^{-1}(y) \} \}. \\ &\geq \min \{ \sup \{ \min \{ A(b), X(a) \} \mid a = f^{-1}(x), b = f^{-1}(y) \} \}. \\ &\geq \min \{ f(A) (y), Y(x) \}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $f(A)$ is a normal fuzzy submodule of Y .

(2) $f^{-1}(B)$ is fuzzy submodule of X by proposition (1.2.4).

To prove $f^{-1}(B)$ is normal. Let $a, b \in R$ such that $f(a) = x, f(b) = y$, where $x, y \in R'$.

$$\begin{aligned} f^{-1}(B) (a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a) &= f^{-1}(B) (f^{-1}(x^{-1}) \cdot f^{-1}(y) \cdot f^{-1}(x)) = f^{-1}[B(x^{-1} \cdot y \cdot x)] . \\ &\geq f[\min \{ B(y), Y(x) \}]. \\ &= \sup \{ \min \{ \min \{ B(y), Y(x) \} \mid x = f(a), y = f(b) \} \}. \\ &\geq \min \{ \sup \{ \min \{ B(y), Y(x) \} \mid f(a) = x, f(b) = y \} \}. \\ &\geq \min \{ f^{-1}(B) (b), X(a) \}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $f^{-1}(B)$ is a normal fuzzy submodule of X .

2.2 FUNDAMENTAL THEOREMS

(First Fuzzy Isomorphism Theorem For Fuzzy Modules)

THEOREM 2.2.1 :

Let X and Y are fuzzy modules over fuzzy ring of R and f be onto homomorphism between them. Then $X / \ker f_{zzf} \approx f(X)$.

PROOF:

Define $g: R/\ker f \rightarrow f(R)$ such that: $g(a + \ker f) = f(a)$, for each $a + \ker f \in R/\ker f$.

By definition, g is a non empty function of $R/\ker f$ since $g(0 + \ker f) = f(0)$

Let $a + \ker f, b + \ker f \in R/\ker f$, $a + \ker f = b + \ker f$ implies that $a - b \in \ker f$, therefore $f(a - b) = 0'$ and f is homomorphism, then $f(a) - f(b) = 0'$ implies $f(a) = f(b)$. Thus $g(a + \ker f) = g(b + \ker f)$. Hence g is well - define.

Now, we must prove g is an isomorphism

First, if $g(a + \ker f) = g(b + \ker f)$, then $f(a) = f(b)$ and $f(a) - f(b) = 0'$ implies that $f(a - b) = 0'$. Thus $a - b \in \ker f$ therefore $a + \ker f = b + \ker f$, g is one - to - one.

Second, for any $b \in f(R)$ there exists $a \in R$ such that: $f(a) = b$ since f is onto then $f(a) = g(a + \ker f) = b$, g is onto.

Finally, Let $a + \ker f, b + \ker f \in R/\ker f$

$$\begin{aligned} g[(a + \ker f) \oplus (b + \ker f)] &= g[(a + b) + \ker f] = f(a + b) = f(a) + f(b) \\ &= g(a + \ker f) + g(b + \ker f) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} g[(a + \ker f) \otimes (b + \ker f)] &= g[(a \cdot b) + \ker f] = f(a \cdot b) = f(a) \cdot f(b) \\ &= g(a + \ker f) \cdot g(b + \ker f) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Moreover, } X / \ker f_{zzf}(a + \ker f) &= \sup\{X / \ker f_{zzf}(a + \ker f) \mid a + \ker f \in \ker f_{zzf}\} \\ &= X(a) = f(X)(f(a)) \text{ where } f(X)(a + \ker f) = \sup\{X(b) \mid b \in f^{-1}(f(a))\} \\ &= Y(f^{-1}(a)) = X(a). \end{aligned}$$

Hence $X / \ker f_{zzf} \approx f(X)$.

(Second Fuzzy Isomorphism Theorem For Fuzzy Modules)

THEOREM 2.2.2 :

Let A and B be fuzzy submodules of a fuzzy ring X of R , with $A \subseteq B$ such that $A^* = B^*$ (i.e. $B(x) = B(0)$, whenever $A(x) = A(0)$). Then $(X / A) / (B / A) \approx (X / B)$.

PROOF:

B / A is a normal fuzzy submodule of X / A by proposition (1.3.5), by proposition (2.1.10).

Let $B/A(x + I_1) = B(x)$ where I_1 is the normal submodule of X maximal among those contained in $A^* \cap X^*$, because $B/A(x + I_1) = \max \{B(y) \mid y + I_1 = x + I_1\}$ and since $y^{-1} \cdot x \in A^*$, we have $y^{-1} \cdot x \in B^*$ and therefore $B(y) = B(x)$.

$(X/A)^* = X/I_1$ and $(B/A)^* = B^*/I_1$.

So, the normal submodule of X/I_1 maximal among those contained in $(X/A)^* \cap (B/A)^*$ may be written as I_2/I_1 , where I_2 is the normal submodule of X maximal among those contained in $X^* \cap B^*$.

It is well known that $f: (X/I_1)/(I_2/I_1) \rightarrow X/I_2$ such that :

$f(x + I_1 + (I_2/I_1)) = x + I_2$ is an isomorphism by remark (1.2.3).

Moreover, $(X/A)/(B/A)(x + I_1 + (I_2/I_1)) = X/A(x + I_1)$.
 $= X(x) = X/B(x + I_2)$.

Hence $(X/A)/(B/A) \approx (X/B)$.

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نظرية التماثل الضبابية

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المستخلص

في عام 1965 (Zadeh L.A.) قدم مفهوم المجموعات الضبابية (fuzzy sets) وفي عام 1982 (Liu W.J.) صاغ مصطلح الحلقة الضبابية (fuzzy ring) و عرفها وعرف مفهوم المثالي الضبابي (fuzzy ideal) ومنذ ذلك الحين أجريت العديد من البحوث في مختلف المجالات الرياضية النظرية و التطبيقية حول هذا الموضوع.

وفي عام 1993 (Liu W.J.) صاغ مصطلح الموديول الضبابية (fuzzy submodule) . أن الهدف الرئيسي من هذا البحث هو تقديم بعض التعاريف والمبرهنات الأساسية في ما يتعلق في النواة الضبابية (kernel fuzzy) التي عرفت وذكرت شروطها التي يمكن استخدامها للحصول على ما نريد من homomorphism و isomorphism.